

Eukaryotes

Eukaryotes

Prokaryotes

Bacteria

Bacteria

Bacteria

Bacteria

Archaea

Bacteria

*Carpediemonas frisia*

*Carpediemonas membranifera*

Bacteria

Bacteria

Archaea

Bacteria

Bacteria

Bacteria

Bacteria

Bacteria

Prokaryotes

Bacteria

Prokaryotes

0.5

